

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP4 – Establishment of a non-commercial, Europe-wide breast milk biobank and analytical centre

D4.7 Report with standardized procedures for biobank sample analysis

Lead contributor	Erik Melander, Uppsala University
Other contributors	4.BBMRI-ERIC 14. Universitetet i Oslo 21. Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse 24. Université de Geneva, University Hospital in Lausanne (CHUV) 38. Novartis Pharma AG 47 UCB Biopharma SPRI

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.1	29-11-2024	

Abstract

In this report we describe the procedures for biobank sample analysis of human breast milk and plasma samples of cetirizine, venlafaxine, metformin, and prednisolone, as well as the active metabolite of venlafaxine; O-desmethylvenlafaxine from lactation studies from the ConcePTION project. The methods were developed and validated for analysis on a UHPLC-MS/MS system with a rapid chromatographic gradient allowing for the analysis of all studied compounds within 3 minutes per run. We validated stability, dilution integrity, accuracy and precision of the method, calibration curve range, selectivity and specificity, determination of lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) in the relevant matrices.

The validation confirmed that all parameters were within the acceptance criteria described in the regulatory guidelines and that the stability of the compounds in human whole blood, plasma and breast milk was sufficient for the logistics of the demonstration studies, allowing for the processing and handling of the samples prior to analysis.

The validated methods were applied to the analysis of samples from the performed lactation studies, successfully quantifying the compounds in the clinical samples and describing the pharmacokinetics of cetirizine in human breast milk. The data from the cetirizine study was used to develop a population pharmacokinetic model of cetirizine in human breast milk and estimating relative infant dose.

Methods

In order to properly measure the concentration of drugs in human breast milk and plasma, standardized and validated methods are necessary. In order to achieve this regulatory guidelines from the FDA (Bioanalytical Method Validation Guidance)¹ and EMA (Guideline on bioanalytical method validation)² were followed to validate analytical methods for cetirizine, venlafaxine, metformin, and prednisolone, as well as the metabolite of venlafaxine; O-desmethylvenlafaxine. In order to achieve fast, reproducible and accurate analysis a LC-MS/MS based approach was taken since all studied drugs were small molecules.

The validation aimed to validate the following parameters: stability, dilution integrity, accuracy and precision of the method, calibration curve range, selectivity and specificity, determination of lower limit of quantification (LLOQ). All parameters were validated in the relevant matrix (human breast milk and/or plasma) based on the planned demonstration studies. Stability was also assessed in human whole blood. Plasma was collected from whole blood samples by centrifugation for 10 minutes at 1500 x g at 4°C. Matrix effects were assessed in human breast milk and plasma.

For all studied compounds the same instrumentation was used, being a Waters Xevo TQ-S micro triple quadrupole mass spectrometer, with a Waters Acquity UHPLC used for chromatographic separation on an Acquity BEH C18 column (inner diameter 2.1 x 50 mm, particle size 1.7 µm, and pore size 130 Å). For separation of cetirizine, venlafaxine, O-desmethylvenlafaxine, and prednisolone, mobile phases consisting of 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid in water (Mobile phase A) or acetonitrile (Mobile phase B) were used. For the separation of metformin mobile phases consisting of 0.05 % heptafluorobutyric acid and 0.05 % propionic acid in water (Mobile phase C) or acetonitrile (Mobile phase D) were used. The chromatographic separation had a total run time of 3 minutes per sample. The mass spectrometer was operated in selected reaction monitoring mode, with specific ion pairs for each studied compound and internal standard.

Three separate validations were ran, one for cetirizine, venlafaxine, and O-desmethylvenlafaxine, one for metformin, and one for prednisolone³. Data acquisition was performed using the MassLynx (version 4.2) software. The compound peaks were integrated and quantified with TargetLynx

(version 4.1) based on the peak area ratio of the target compound and the internal standard from linear regression.

Milk and plasma samples were collected by the respective demonstration study and shipped to Uppsala biobank where the samples were aliquoted and stored at -80°C pending analysis. When samples were received at Uppsala University for analysis they were stored at -20°C.

Sample analysis was performed by taking 40 µL sample and precipitating proteins by adding three volumes of acetonitrile with internal standard on a 96-well plate. After centrifugation 60 µL of the supernatant was transferred to a new sample plate and diluted with 110 µL of water with internal standard. The sample plate was then transferred to the UHPLC-MS/MS system for analysis.

Results

The validated methods were able to quantify cetirizine, venlafaxine, O-desmethylvenlafaxine, metformin, and prednisolone with precision and accuracy within the regulatory guidelines (CV < 15%, bias ± 15%). Full validation results for all methods can be found in the listed validation reports. Deuterated internal standards were selected for all analytes to provide accurate quantification. The short term stability in room temperature was confirmed to be 72 hours and 7 days in 4°C. The long term stability in -20°C and -80°C was confirmed to be 365 days. This provides the opportunity to store samples and re-analyse them at later time points.

The standard curve range was determined to be 1-500 nM for cetirizine, venlafaxine, and O-desmethylvenlafaxine, and 5-1500 nM for metformin and prednisolone. Appropriate quality control (QC) samples were determined and applied for the accuracy and precision assessment. These QC samples were included in all future analyses to ensure that the analysis conformed to the validated standards. Lower limit of quantification assessment samples were tested and conformed to the regulatory guidelines. This allowed for the determination of drug concentration in samples from demonstration studies and characterization of the pharmacokinetic (PK) profile of the drugs in milk and or plasma. Should drug concentrations in the samples be higher than the highest point in the standard curve, the dilution integrity of samples was determined to be accurate up to 20-fold dilution.

The selectivity and specificity were tested in all matrices (human breast milk and plasma) and the matrix effect was assessed and these were all found to be within the acceptance criteria according to the regulatory guidelines. No interference was found from endogenous compounds or metabolites. In all analysis runs of samples from lactation studies blanks samples were included to ensure that no carry-over effects were seen.

The method was used for the analysis of samples from lactation studies of cetirizine⁴, venlafaxine, metformin, and prednisolone and was able to quantify the concentration of the compounds from all these demonstration studies in a rapid and accurate way. These results will be able to be used for the determination of pharmacokinetic parameters of the drugs in human breast milk and/or plasma, and for the determination of milk transfer parameters to assess the compatibility of usage of the drugs whilst breastfeeding.

The quantified concentrations from the lactation study of cetirizine were used to develop a population pharmacokinetic model of cetirizine in human breast milk, describing the concentration-time profile, assessing the impact of population characteristics such as body weight and age, and estimating the relative infant dose based on model predicted milk concentrations in the mother⁵.

Discussion

The procedures for bioanalysis of biobank samples from lactation studies provide guidance for how to set up analytical processes for the rapid and accurate analysis of human breast milk and plasma samples. Of key importance is the validation of stability in both milk and plasma, as well as in human whole blood, as this will guide timelines for sample processing and handling in conjunction with the lactation studies. Whole blood stability will regulate how quickly blood samples need to be centrifuged and plasma removed, and room temperature and 4°C stability will regulate how quickly samples need to be frozen. Validated stability will increase confidence in the bioanalytical results and any following conclusion. A short stability in whole blood increases demands on the capabilities on the clinical centre performing the lactation study as they will need to have the capabilities to centrifuge the blood on site.

The standardized procedures for sample preparation and analysis, where all compounds are able to be treated in the same way, with the same sample preparation, analysis on the same type of 96-well plate and on the same instrument provide a robust method that is easily described and transferrable. Another benefit of the developed analytical methods is that two of the three methods are using the same mobile phases, leading to easier analysis, and less complexity and need for specialised chemicals.

The method described herein is rapid, robust, and capable of quantifying the compounds of interest in a range relevant to clinical concentrations. The low LLOQs in the single digit nanomolar range are important as the transfer of drugs into breast milk can lead to low concentrations, especially at time points hours after dose intake. Being able to determine these concentrations is crucial for the determination of PK parameters, comparison to published PK data and performing popPK modelling.

The value of performing proper validation of the analytical methods according to regulatory guidelines should not be understated, as this increases confidence in the results from lactation studies, even ones performed in a primarily academic setting, and increases the chance of the results being used either in clinic or on the label of the drug in question. By setting up these procedures for the bioanalysis of samples from lactation studies we provide a framework for future studies to build upon.

Conclusion

In this report we present three simple, rapid, specific, and sensitive methods for the (1) simultaneous quantification of cetirizine, venlafaxine, and *O*-desmethylvenlafaxine in human breast milk, (2) quantification of metformin in human breast milk or plasma, and (3) quantification of prednisolone in human breast milk or plasma. The methods provided have high sensitivity, allowing for the quantification of low drug concentrations in clinical samples, and provide stability data of high importance for lactation study planning and logistics.

List of validation reports

ValidationReport_CetirizineVenlafaxineo-desmethylvenlafaxine_Milk_CW210916
ValidationReport_MetforminMilk_CW210921
ValidationReport_MetforminPlasma_CWEM240912
ValidationReport_PrednisoloneMilk_EM241003
ValidationReport_PrednisolonePlasma_EM241003

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<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/bioanalytical-method-validation-scientific-guideline> (2012).
3. Wegler, C. *et al.* Simple and rapid quantification of cetirizine, venlafaxine, and O-desmethylvenlafaxine in human breast milk, and metformin in human milk and plasma with UHPLC-MS/MS. *J. Chromatogr. B Analyt. Technol. Biomed. Life. Sci.* **1205**, 123340 (2022).
4. Nordeng, H. *et al.* Transfer of cetirizine/levocetirizine into human breast milk and estimation of drug exposure to infants through breastfeeding: A human lactation study from the ConcePTION project. *Basic Clin. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* (2023) doi:10.1111/bcpt.13948.
5. Melander, E. *et al.* Population pharmacokinetic modelling of cetirizine concentrations in human breast milk-A contribution from the ConcePTION project. *Basic Clin. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* (2024) doi:10.1111/bcpt.14100.

